

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Source citation (Turabian 2013, 85)
2. Author-Date Style (Turabian 2013, 128)
3. Note-Bibliography (Turabian 2013, 90)
4. Rules of Style (Turabian 2013, 162)
5. Turabian Rule of Style (Turabian 2013, 162)

TURABIAN RULE OF STYLE

1) INTRODUCTION

Part II of the book of “A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertation” (Turabian 2013) vividly covers a comprehensive source of citations using the styles of note-bibliography and author-date styles and their basic patterns as well as specific citations of sources of book, journal, magazine, government documents, published, unpublished, electronic online, musical etc. which the writers can use to back up his/her propositions. According to the scholar, “When the style works best, ideas flow logically, sources are credited appropriately and papers are organized predictably and consistently” (APA 2020, 15). Moreover, the second part of the book unveils the reason for source citations and requirements, describe the note-bibliography and author-date source citation styles for specific documents that the writer can utilize in the research. On the other hand, the third part of the book dwells on spelling, punctuation, abbreviations, quotation, tables, and figures that help to sharpen the saw to guide the writers to deliver meaningful messages.

In summary, parts II and III of “A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertation” lay the foundation and state basic instruments that guide the writer to follow standard norms, principles, and facts that enhance the authenticity of the issues under consideration. Indeed, these parts depict the roadmap for writers, editors, and

translators who are working in academic or business areas on how to use the appropriate sources of citations and use correct spelling and punctuation styles to communicate concisely with readers or larger audiences.

2) SOURCE CITATION

To begin with, the book clearly states the reason for source citations and requirements to consider during the process. In academic research discovery of new approach, methods, and ideas that transform human nature and environment requires not only proposal of new ways of doing a thing but also citations of sources from similar or contrary perspectives that makes citation of sources in the document quite important. As to Turabian, “Source citations must always provide sufficient information either to lead readers directly to the sources consulted or, for materials that may not be readily available, to enable readers to positively identify them, regardless of whether the sources are published or unpublished” (Turabian 2013, 75). The norm, rules, and principles that underlie and govern how things operate always affect our beliefs, behavior, and action that follow. Hence, the idea that generates and advances innovation should pass the existing mode and mechanism that accultured to the academic arena. I do agree with the idea that for your premise to be accepted by others it should be back up from other sources through the standard style of communication that others can accept, convinced about your postulate, or proposal to make a part of their daily knowledge and action to be taken. Your success as a researcher thus depends not just on how well you gather and analyze data but on how you report your reasoning so that your readers can test and judge it before making them part of your claim of their knowledge and understanding (Turabian 2013, 15).

On top of that the researcher to persuade and convince the readers about his/her outcomes, the readers expect the researcher to supplement his work with the fact that is associated with his project from other sources. Similarly, the readers are highly influenced by the fact presented to them from other sources to advance their skills and knowledge with regards to the issue under consideration. According to the scholar, “There are three reasons to cite the materials you use first to give credit to others’ work and ideas; second to show readers the materials on which you base your analysis and third to guide readers to the materials you have used so they can examine it for themselves” (Lipson 2006, 12).

a) Author-Date Style

Author-date style citations as the name indicate author-date style give focus to the author and its date of publication. This style of citation is particularly used in-text citations. As to Turabian, The order of elements in reference list entries follows the same general pattern for all types of sources: author, date of publication, title, other facts of publication. Indeed, it is imperative to follow these in-text citations for the writer to back up his premises and hypothesis in the reporting.

b) Note-Bibliography Style

Note-Bibliography citations and referencing style are used to cite a specific book, journal, magazine, unpublished, published, government documents, and online sources to name a few. To this end, the footnote/endnote shed light on the subject matters to enhance the understanding, meaning connotated with the issue under analysis whereas the bibliography referencing the sources used in the documents stating the name of the author, editor, the title, place of publication, publications agent, year of publication at the end of the report. According to Turabian, “Citations of books may include a wide range of elements such as the name of the author, title, editions, volume, series, facts about the publications” (Turabian 2013, 102). That other style worth noticing is to be considered is author-date-style that is explained in next point.

3) RULES OF STYLE

The researcher must decide which type of style she/he used in communicating her/his messages to larger audiences. Different fields have different styles to follow to convey their meaning. Style provides a foundation for effective scholarly communication because it helps authors present their ideas in a clear, concise, and organized manner (APA 2020, 15). The USA and UK style has their formatting. Academic writers need to be sure that their communications are written in the appropriate style (Swales and Feak 2012). The style being used in the text always has its implication and meaning associated with it as per identified audience and groups. Different fields used different types of styles. According to Steven Terrell, “Papers requiring literature to be referenced generally have a specific formatting style that the publishers, the university, or the professors prefer. There are many such styles: The Modern Language Association (MLA), The Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), and the American Psychological Association (APA) style.” In the same manner, the type of style we pursue will influence the structure of sentence, punctuation, capitalization, common, spelling format to be used in the documents.

4) TURABIAN RULE OF STYLE

The specific basic pattern of citations varied according to the field of studies and school of thought in which they utilized different methods of citations. As per the Chicago manual style-Turabian rule which was named after the Kate Turabian of Chicago University who started to state how the writers of research dissertations, papers, and theses frame their report writing for larger audiences. According to Charles, “There are three major citation styles: Chicago (or Turabian) used in many fields, Modern Language Association (MLA) used in the humanities and American Psychological Associations (APA) used in social sciences, education, engineering, and business.” He also asserted that Several sciences have developed their distinctive styles. It is imperative to follow the mode of your styles according to your academic fields, Universities, and instructor’s guidance to which citations and referencing styles to be used. To this end, the style truly affects the format, spelling, punctuations, and figures that in turn shape the communication and inference of

the subject matters under consideration. In connection with this, it is important to consider the note-bibliography-specific style of citation of different sources that are used in Chicago Manual of Style.

5) CONCLUSION

The Chicago Manual Style of writing papers, theses, and dissertation is an excellent instrument for researchers and writers for conveying his/her messages and ideas vividly and precisely. Indeed, the manual presents a roadmap and dependable perspectives to communicate meaningful ideas across various fields of study. Moreover, it also guides the writer on how to use appropriate source citations of books, journals, magazines, published, unpublished, government documents to enhance the authenticity and credibility of the issues under consideration. Furthermore, the second part of the manual states the use of footnote/endnote in the writing to clarify and deepen the understanding of the readers. Apart from this, the manual also describes Note-bibliography and author-date style of source citations and referencing styles used in the writing. Whereas the third part of the book deals with spelling, punctuation, tables, and figures for delivering eloquent ideas.

Finally, I am greatly impressed and recommend the Chicago Manual Styles of Papers, Theses, and Dissertations for the researcher to use to get academic writing in a very standard fashion to convey clear, vivid, and concise communication of messages across various fields.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.